

Modifications of a windscanner

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This project deal with the first step in designing a new type of wind scanner. The new type of scanner is supposed to be place inside the hub of a wind turbine. By analyzing the wind in front of the mille we will be able to adjust the mille correct and therefore increase the power output.

The presentation will be based on my bachelor project there is in progress to be written this semester in cooperation with DTU Risø and IPU.

Through the presentation I will speech about the following subjects:

- A short presentation of the technical principle in a common windscanner
- Application and perspective fore scanning the wind
- The problematic in the existing system
- Finding the optimal pattern
- Concept ideas
- Choosing the right concept
- Optimizing the final concept
- if possible some test of the system